

New European Bauhaus Academy

The NEBA Alliance:
a European network of training hubs

1st New European Bauhaus Academy Conference

Barcelona, February 27, 2026

Andreja Kutnar
University of Primorska

Circular Bio-based Europe
Joint Undertaking

New European Bauhaus Academy

Co-designing the Alliance :
An open journey

Berlin meeting, 10 April 2025

Co-designing the Alliance

Why a NEB Academy?

To accelerate Europe's shift towards a **climate-neutral built environment** by fostering the **skills, education, innovation, mindsets, and collaborations** needed for systemic change !

NEB Academy Mission

To train, upskill, and reskill the construction ecosystem to achieve a carbon neutral building sector and a beautiful, sustainable, and inclusive transformation of the built environment.

**NEB
Academy
Manifesto**

NEB Academy Mission

2024-2026

European training ecosystem of NEBA Hubs and pilot training activities.

NEB Academy receives a key role in strategic documents of the EU.

2026-2030

The NEB Academy:

- offers micro-credentials and other training formats that are transferable across Europe
- shaping the educational, skills, and innovation policies of the EU
- Key partner in NEB Facility and Horizon Europe funding programs

2034 onwards

The NEB Academy:

- is present in all continents
- has key role in achieving breakthrough innovations in the construction sector
- is acknowledged as main contributor to sustainable, inclusive, and beautiful future

For who?

TG1

Education, training, and academia.

TG3

Public bodies and policy makers

TG2

Construction ecosystem, private sector.

TG4

General public and civil society.

NEB Academy Hubs in Europe

NEBA Alliance

- 14 partners from 11 countries
- 5 NEBA Hubs
- > 20 pilot trainings implemented
- Building up NEB Academy

Tallinn meeting, 9 Oct 2024

NEB Academy Hubs in Europe

NEBA Alliance

- 14 partners from 11 countries
- 5 NEBA Hubs
- > 20 pilot trainings implemented
- Building up NEB Academy

- NEBA South Hub
- NEBA North Hub
- NEBA Outreach Hub
- NEBAP Hub
- NEBA Central Hub

NEB Academy growth

- + 14 partners
- + 25 new institutions
- + 11 new countries

Grants for training courses and materials

10 Grants; 6 countries

3 Spain

2 Netherlands

2 Poland

1 Bosnia & Hercegovina

1 Czechia

1 Greece

Grants for training courses and materials

10 Grants; 6 countries

1. Volupte Studio (Spain)
2. Fondacija Novi evropski Bauhaus za Bosnu I Hercegovinu-NEB4BiH (BiH)
3. Urbana (Greece)
4. Julia Steketeer - BAGACEIRA Material Research & Design (Spain)
5. Stowarzyszenie Badawczo-Animacyjnej Flaneur (Poland)
6. Contexts Beata Patuszynska (Poland)
7. STICHTING, INSTITUTE FOR URBAN EXCELLENCE & Studio Barnard (Netherlands)
8. Atelier La Juntana – Armor Gutierrez Rivas (Spain)
9. Nationaal Kennis Centrum Biobased Bouw (Netherlands)
10. Centrum pro podporu podnikání a zaměstnanosti, z.ú. (Czech Republic)

Grants for partnering with NEBA hubs

7 Grants

18 institutions

9 countries

Grants for partnering with NEBA hubs

7 Grants

1. University of Beira Interior / C-MADE Centre of Materials and Civil Engineering for Sustainability (Portugal)
2. The Estonian Union of Co-operative Housing Associations (Estonia)
3. VILNIAUS GEDIMINO TECHNIKOS UNIVERSITETAS (Lithuania)
4. CLUSTER LEGNO ARREDO E SISTEMA CASA FVG SRL CONSORTILE (Italy)
5. BDO Consulting LLC (Ukraine)
6. SocialTech Lab (Cyprus)
7. MOZAIK Institute - institution for adult education (Croatia)

How to NEB Academy make a self sustainable entity?

Codesign with an EU-wide Alliance

NEB Academy Hubs in Europe

Established leading NEBA Hubs and first training activities

More than **5,000 participants** joined the in-person trainings.

48 training courses on the **NEBA online platform**

Cascade grants involved additional **28** partners

About **500** certificates delivered

Build the foundation for the NEB Academy

Built up a Community of Practice

Initiated a Skills Agenda and
Policy Roadmap

Build the foundation for the NEB Academy

- ✓ Identified relevant **stakeholders, knowledge gaps, and training needs** at Hub level
- ✓ The **NEBA Recognition Framework** - course recognition and quality assurance

NEBA's advocacy on the **policy level**.

- Wood4Bauhaus
- WoodPoP
- Policy recommendations for the NEB

NEB Academy beyond Europe

Making international connections to
make a global impact

- ✓ **Reach a global audience:**
Link to international partners in Ukraine, Japan, Brazil, Canada
- ✓ **NEBA's online platform** is ready to scale.
- ✓ **Dissemination & Communication** at conferences, in the press, at workshops, and in through integration in scientific work.

Reshaping higher education

NEB Academy highlights need for existing educational programmes to change

✓ **New Wood Innovation for Sustainability study program at NEBAP HUB**

- Strong involvement of industry
- Mobility window at NEBA Alliance partners
- Innovative teaching methods
- Obligatory course - Buildings Design driven by New European Bauhaus

Why a NEB Academy?

To accelerate Europe's shift towards a **climate-neutral built environment** by fostering the **skills, education, innovation, mindsets, and collaborations** needed for systemic change !

Building with natural materials

nature

[Explore content](#) ▾ [About the journal](#) ▾ [Publish with us](#) ▾

[nature](#) > [articles](#) > [article](#)

Article | [Open access](#) | [Published: 20 September 2023](#)

Evidence for the earliest structural use of wood at least 476,000 years ago

[L. Barham](#) , [G. A. T. Duller](#), [I. Candy](#), [C. Scott](#), [C. R. Cartwright](#), [J. R. Peterson](#), [C. Kabukcu](#), [M. S. Chapot](#), [F. Melia](#), [V. Rots](#), [N. George](#), [N. Taipale](#), [P. Gethin](#) & [P. Nkombwe](#)

[Nature](#) **622**, 107–111 (2023) | [Cite this article](#)

135k Accesses | **1** Citations | **3672** Altmetric | [Metrics](#)

Is this the reason people feel good in buildings with wood?

Building with natural materials

Well
designed
structures
can last for
centuries.

Japan

Norway

Mali

We need to educate, innovate, and look back

**We need to connect
the new with the old.**

Knowledge & Skills & Innovation are Europe's competitive advantage

Skills to master material

Skills to co-create and design

Skills to leverage new tech

Skills for social inclusion

Value of skills in biomaterials

Stradivari violin

Mona Lisa

0,005 m³ (77 cm x 53 cm x 1,3 cm)

1 billion EUR

New European
Bauhaus Academy

Driving innovation

Research & Innovation

2024 - 2028

Make better
use of
underutilised
wood in NEB

HORIZON-CL6-2024-CLIMATE-01-5

2024 - 2028

Sustainable
innovation to
support
timber in
NEB

HORIZON-CL6-2024-CLIMATE-01-5

Ambient

Coming soon!

Improve public
procurement for
advanced
materials to
support NEB

HORIZON-CL4-INDUSTRY-2025-01-MATERIALS-44

 New European
Bauhaus Academy

Strong in policy

Strasbourg, 16.12.2025
COM(2025) 1026 final

**COMMUNICATION FROM THE COMMISSION TO THE EUROPEAN
PARLIAMENT, THE COUNCIL, THE EUROPEAN ECONOMIC AND SOCIAL
COMMITTEE AND THE COMMITTEE OF THE REGIONS**

New European Bauhaus - from vision to implementation

Bioeconomy Strategy (November 2025)

The European affordable housing plan
(December 2025)

Communication 'New European Bauhaus:
From vision to implementation (December 2025)

Policy: NEB Academy going global

<https://www.bmluk.gv.at/en/coli>

Policy: DARA Award

1ST DARA AWARD CEREMONY

26 NOV 2026

DARA AWARD 2026

Celebrating Sustainable Timber Construction

Prague, Czechia

What comes next?

**Establish a Strong
NEB Academy Brand**

**Transform the NEBA Platform into
a Premier Training Marketplace**

Develop a Rigorous Quality Assurance Framework

Codesign a Sustainable Business Model for Long-Term Viability

Founding Manifesto of the New European Bauhaus Academy

Welcome Commit

Build together

Affirm

Insist

Emphasize

Confirm

Guarantee

Recognise

Invite

 New European
Bauhaus Academy

Joins us by signing it today and be
part of its further development!